

Variations in Political Trolling Tactics Towards Democrat and Republican Candidates Between two US Presidential Election Cycles

Fichman, Pnina Indiana University, USA | fichman@indiana.edu
Akter, Shohana Indiana University, USA | sakter@iu.edu
Rathi, Maanvi Indiana University, USA | mrathi@iu.edu
Rutherford, Tess Indiana University, USA | teruther@iu.edu
Dolliff, Lily Indiana University, USA | ldolliff@iu.edu

ABSTRACT

Major efforts to combat disinformation and trolling on Twitter, due to its impact on election results across the globe, have been documented while trolling seems to be as prevalent as ever before. We aim to examine if and how the extent of trolling toward political figures on Twitter changed between the 2016 and 2020 US presidential election cycles, analyzing outrage comments made towards Tweets by 20 Democrat and Republican candidates for President/VP and Senate/House. Based on content analysis of 9,461 comments, we found significantly more trolling towards Republicans than Democrats, both for presidential candidates, as well as candidates for the Senate and the House, demonstrating trolling asymmetry. We also found that between 2016 and 2020 there was a significant increase in overall trolling and in trolling towards Republicans, but not in overall trolling towards President/VP candidates, highlighting the increase in domestic trolling rather than external interference in election results.

KEYWORDS

Political trolling, Trolling asymmetry, Twitter

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

“Trolling is an umbrella term for a spectrum of multidimensional, antagonistic, antisocial, or deviant behaviors and motivations online, [involving any] behavior intended to provoke a reaction in another user” (Ortiz, 2020, p. 1), that varies across different online communities and platforms (Sanfillipo et al., 2017). However, online trolling includes not only antisocial online behavior (Cruz et al., 2018), but also political and ideological trolling (Sanfilippo et al., 2017) that often involves political satire (Fichman, 2020) and humor (Sanfillipo et al., 2017). Moreover, trolling commonly refers to state-sponsored trolling such as the Russian troll farms (Zalenkauskaitė & Niezgodna, 2017) and the IRA involvement in the US presidential elections (Kim, et al., 2019). Trolling often leads to mis/disinformation (Fichman & Vaughn, 2021; Norri-Sederholm, 2020), intensifies political polarization (Bulut & Yörük, 2017), and, in extreme cases, can even result in victim suicide (Coles & West, 2016). It has become increasingly critical to study political trolling as political discussion online has grown in recent years, alongside the rise of online political conversation and as political digital ad spending per year has increased from 1.79 billion dollars in 2018 to 2.84 billion dollars in 2019 (Dixon, 2022).

While social media platforms may be an “important outlet for political expression” (Asenas & Hubble, 2018, p. 37), these platforms do not always foster civil discourse necessary to support democracy, and instead they enable toxic disinhibition (Suler, 2004) and posts with a range of outrage tactics (Sobieraj & Berry, 2011). Political trolling includes baiting opponents into conflict while facing unique challenges of internal integration and community buildings (Flores-Saviaga et al., 2018) and provoking outrage (Lieback, 2019; Sobieraj & Berry, 2011) to increase the divide between different sides of the political spectrum (Fichman & Rathi, 2022). Social media plays a major role in sharing and disseminating trolling activities either as political bigshots (Brady, et al., 2019), or by politically engaged individuals (Dvir-Gvirzman et al., 2022; Murdani et al., 2022). There was a significant increase in efforts to develop sociotechnical mechanisms between the 2016 and 2020 election cycles to combat trolling and the spread of disinformation through efforts to combat and block state-sponsored troll bot accounts. “Though the 2020 presidential election was not marked by substantial bot activity or foreign interference, Trump-supporting accounts and media outlets appear to have engaged in the promotion of a “disinformation campaign” ... full of false, misleading, or unverifiable claims about voting fraud” (Kennedy et al., 2022, p.5), creating a dire need to conduct a longitudinal study of trolling as well. This study focuses on the prevalence of online political trolling on Twitter during two US presidential election cycles (2016 & 2020).

In addition to the possible change in the nature and extent of trolling between these two elections, there is evidence of online asymmetry between Democrats and Republicans, not only in the use of social media platforms, but also in the extent that they view, redistribute, and believe in disinformation (e.g., Grossmann & Hopkins, 2019; Linvill & Warren, 2021). Because trolling and disinformation feed each other, we can expect to find trolling asymmetry, but it

is unclear still if the asymmetry will persist, increase, decrease or change its nature over time. Thus, this study examines not only the variations in trolling over time, but also, variations in trolling between Republicans and Democrats, addressing the question: How did trolling towards Republicans and Democrats on Twitter change between the 2016 and 2020 US presidential election cycles?

METHOD

To address the research question, we chose to collect data from Twitter because the platform has become the breeding ground for political trolling; “a study of 134,000 offensive social media posts found that 88% of these posts occur on Twitter” (Case & King, 2018, p. 2). We collected the data between 10/7/2020-11/3/2020, using ExportComments.com from 20 politician accounts, from both parties, Democrats and Republicans, including the accounts of the President and Vice President candidates, as well as randomly selected candidates for the House and for the Senate from both parties. Because Trump, Pence, and Pelosi were included in both elections, the 20 accounts include 17 individuals (Table 1). From each of the 20 accounts we sampled the most recent 20 tweets (400 tweets) and up to 25 comments per tweet, (for a total of 9,461 comments, which is short of 10,000 because two accounts, Duckworth and Schumer, didn't have as many comments per tweet).

	2016	Party	Post	2020	Party	Post
President/ VP	Hillary Clinton	D	President	Joe Biden	D	President
	Donald Trump	R	President	Donald Trump	R	President
	Tim Kaine	D	VP	Kamala Harris	D	VP
	Mike Pence	R	VP	Mike Pence	R	VP
House/ Senate	Tammy Duckworth	D	IL Senate	Ilhan Omar	D	NY Rep
	Nancy Pelosi	D	CA Rep	Alexandria Ocasio-Cortez	D	NY Rep
	Chuck Schumer	D	NY Senate	Nancy Pelosi	D	CA Rep
	Paul Ryan	R	WI Rep	Lindsey Graham	R	SC Senate
	Marco Rubio	R	FL Senate	Mitch McConnell	R	KY Senate
	John McCain	R	AZ Senate	Susan Collins	R	ME Senate

Table 1. Candidates Twitter accounts.

Then, we analyzed each of the 9,461 comments by coding the data at the level of an individual comment, using a code book with four trolling outrage tactics that are common in online political discussions (Sobieraj & Berry, 2011): Derailment, Ideological Misalignment, Insulting and Provocation (Table 2). Two coders coded the comments, and interrater reliability was high at 87.8% simple agreement. This was followed by cross-tabulation analysis, using SPSS.

Code	Description	Example
Derailment	Purposefully leading a conversation off track.	The pandemic saved my marriage, who cares about the poverty rates
Ideological Misalignment	Comments made because of a difference in political opinions –differs from extreme attacking and is rather a disagreement.	I think that the vaccines should be illegal, my body my choice.
Insulting	Statements meant to insult an individual or group of people, including name calling and personal attacks.	She’s so stupid that four years ago she was mixing drinks
Provocation	Statements intended to elicit a specific reaction.	VACCINATED WITH WHAT, IS THE MYSTERY!???

Table 2. Codebook.

FINDINGS & DISCUSSIONS

We examined if the extent of trolling varied based on political affiliation (Republicans vs. Democrats) and between the two election cycles (2016 & 2020) both for presidential and House/Senate candidates. We summarize the results of the content analysis of comments in Table 3, showing trolling frequencies per code by election and party. This is followed by the Chi-square results of the difference between parties and by election cycle in Table 4.

Tactics	Position	Election Cycle		Party						
		2016	2020	Democrats			Republicans			Total
				2016	2020	Total	2016	2020	Total	
Derailment	President/ VP	702	594	371	256	627	331	338	669	1296
	House/ Senate	553	568	202	286	488	351	282	633	1121
Ideological Misalign	President/ VP	699	675	361	227	588	338	448	786	1374
	House/ Senate	223	339	59	225	284	164	114	278	562
Insulting	President/ VP	912	870	478	274	752	434	596	1030	1782
	House/ Senate	534	1216	188	424	612	346	792	1138	1750
Provocation	President/ VP	884	831	460	285	745	424	546	970	1715
	House/ Senate	1120	721	443	433	876	677	288	965	1715
Total	President/ VP	3197	2970	1670	1042	2712	1527	1928	3455	6167
	House/ Senate	2430	2844	892	1368	2260	1538	1476	3014	5274

Table 3. Code frequency.

χ^2	Position	Total Trolling	Derailment	Ideological Misalignment	Insulting	Provocation
Party	President/ VP	13.46**	12.91***	1.00	3.20	0.27
	House/Senate	74.95***	0.26	15.15***	66.41***	25.85***
Election	President/ VP	3.69	3.55*	0.66	0.43	0.08
	House/Senate	346.03***	6.07**	10.35***	255.24***	248.03***
Democrats by election	President/ VP	2.80	1.99	0.01	1.73	0.01
	House/Senate	107.10***	0.94	47.51***	26.89***	73.79***
Republicans by election	President/ VP	9.88**	9.37**	0.58	2.52	0.12
	House/Senate	346.98***	6.26**	7.77**	311.21***	207.80***
2016 election by party	President/ VP	0.22	0.13	0.12	0.02	0.02
	House/Senate	14.51***	0	7.02**	0.42	4.58*
2020 election by party	President/ VP	22.52***	20.93***	0.81	6.96**	0.31
	House/Senate	173.05***	0.74	26.70***	77.33***	28.69***

Sig. (*<.05; **<.01; ***<.001)

Table 4. Chi-square results.

We found that from 2016 to 2020 the extent of trolling towards presidential candidates slightly decreased (3197 vs. 2970 respectively), whereas it significantly increased for the other candidates (2430 vs. 2844 respectively). Even though Republican presidential candidates were trolled significantly more than Democrats overall (3455 vs. 2712

respectively) and in the 2020 election cycle (1928 vs. 1042 respectively), they were trolled slightly less than Democrats in 2016 (1527 vs. 1670 respectively). This might be partially explained by the shift in power between the parties during the election, because trolls are more likely to target those in position of power (Fichman & Rathi, 2022); Democrats were in power (President Obama) going into the election in 2016, but Republicans held the power (President Trump) going to the 2020 election cycle. Indeed, power dynamic plays an important role in trolling, where popular people tend to be more frequently the targets of online trolls (Fichman & Rathi, 2022). This is further demonstrated by the higher trolling towards President/VP candidates compared to Senate/House candidates (6127 vs. 5274 respectively). We argue that our findings demonstrate political trolling asymmetry, which manifests ideological asymmetry and echoes the partisan asymmetry in misinformation (Rao et al. 2022). This trolling asymmetry is evident not only in the extent of trolling towards tweets by political candidates, but also in the variations in trolling style (differences in the extent of specific trolling tactics used towards tweets by candidates from both sides of the isle). Indeed, we found significant variations between Republican and Democrat candidates for Senate/House in the extent of most of the specific trolling tactics towards their tweets (ideological misalignment, insulting, and provocation) and more trolling towards Republicans is evident on each of the trolling tactics (Table 3).

A possible explanation for the fact that Republicans were the target of more trolling overall is that in the US, Democrats are more likely to use Twitter than Republicans (Vogel et al., 2021). However, while some users troll politicians whose ideologies they don't agree with (e.g., Democrats trolling Republican candidates), many users troll candidates from their own side to "discipline" or help shape their direction (e.g., Democrats trolling Democrats), just as they would troll their own media outlets (Al-Rawi et al., 2021). Indeed, while most individuals on Twitter interact with those who share their political views, scholars found that "politically motivated individuals provoke interaction by injecting partisan content into information streams whose primary audience consists of ideologically-opposed users" (Conover et al., 2021, p.89). Still, Barbera et al (2015, p.1531) argues that "while evidence [has shown] that liberals were more likely than conservatives to engage in cross-ideological [interactions,...] previous work may have overestimated the degree of ideological segregation in social-media usage." Whether it is Republicans or Democrats that troll the Republican candidates more, the fact is that Republican candidates were trolled more often than their Democrat counterparts.

CONCLUSION

The sociotechnical affordances of social media platforms enable the wide spread of political trolling and promote disinformation that influences election results. Our study makes two significant contributions to research on political trolling by providing initial evidence of political trolling asymmetry and of the asymmetric variations in political trolling over time.

By examining the extent of trolling towards Democrats and Republicans during two election cycles, we identified significant differences in the extent of trolling towards candidates based on their political affiliation overall and in each election cycle, and significant variations in the direction and extent of trolling over time. This trolling asymmetry corresponds with political asymmetry. However, the trolling asymmetry we identified might be a result of the limitations of the study, which is limited to snapshots of data from only two election cycles and based only on analysis of 20 Twitter accounts of politicians; it is possible that a bigger sample of accounts or a longer period might provide a different picture of trolling asymmetry. Still, the benefits and contribution of thematic content analysis to trolling research justifies the sample size, and the result of the snapshots of political trolling is very important as these include major political events. Future research may expand the sample to affirm or refute the existence of trolling asymmetry. Another limitation of our study is that we only examined trolling on one platform, Twitter, and there is still a need to explore trolling asymmetry on other platforms; when trolls target specific political events, they use several socio technical platforms at once (Howard et. al., 2018) but they may use them differently and it is possible that trolling asymmetry may not be evident on other sociotechnical platforms. Furthermore, the rise in political trolling over time that we found might mostly involve domestic trolling, while the external interferences in the 2020 elections from the IRA accounts declined from its level in 2016. Future research may further focus on the differences between external and domestic trolling to discern the influence of global trolling in national politics from the domestic trolling that is driven by the domestic political agenda.

REFERENCES

- Al-Rawi, A., Al-Musalli, A., & Rigor, P. A. (2021). Networked flak in CNN and Fox News memes on Instagram. *Digital Journalism*, 1-18.
- Asenas, J. J., & Hubble, B. (2018). Trolling free speech rallies: Social media practices and the (un) democratic spectacle of dissent. *Taboo: The Journal of Culture and Education*, 17(2), 6, 35-53
- Barberá, P., Jost, J. T., Nagler, J., Tucker, J. A., & Bonneau, R. (2015). Tweeting from left to right: Is online political communication more than an echo chamber? *Psychological Science*, 26(10), 1531–1542.

- Brady, W. J., Wills, J. A., Burkart, D., Jost, J. T., & Van Bavel, J. J. (2019). An ideological asymmetry in the diffusion of moralized content on social media among political leaders. *Journal of The Experimental Psychology: General*, 148(10), 1802-1813.
- Bulut, E., & Yörük, E. (2017). Mediatized populisms| digital populism: Trolls and political polarization of Twitter in Turkey. *International Journal of Communication*, 11, 4093-4117.
- Case, C. J., & King, D. L. (2018). Internet trolling victimization: An empirical examination of incidence in undergraduate business students. *Research in Higher Education Journal*, 34, 1-11.
- Coles, B. A., & West, M. (2016). Trolling the trolls: Online forum users constructions of the nature and properties of trolling. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 60, 233-244.
- Conover, M., Ratkiewicz, J., Francisco, M., Goncalves, B., Menczer, F., & Flammini, A. (2011). Political polarization on Twitter. *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*, July 2011, Barcelona, Spain 5(1), 89-96. <https://doi.org/10.1609/icwsm.v5i1.14126>
- Cruz, A. G. B., Seo, Y., & Rex, M. (2018). Trolling in online communities: A practice-based theoretical perspective. *The Information Society*, 34(1), 15-26.
- Dixon, S. (2022, February 8). Social media and politics in the United States. *Statista Research Department*. Retrieved on March 23rd, 2022. <https://www.statista.com/topics/3723/social-media-and-politics-in-the-united-states/#dossierKeyfigures>
- Dvir -Gvirsman, S., Tsuruel, K., Sheaffer, T., Shenhav, S., Zoizner, A., Lavi, L., ... & Waismel-Manor, I. (2022). Mediated representation at the age of social media: How connection with politicians contributes to citizens' feelings of representation. Evidence from a longitudinal study. *Political Communication*, 39(6), 1-22.
- Dutta, U., Hanscom, R., Zhang, J. S., Han, R., Lehman, T., Lv, Q., & Mishra, S. (2021). Analyzing Twitter users' behavior before and after contact by the Russia's Internet Research Agency. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 5(CSCW1), 1-24.
- Fichman, P. (2022). The role of culture and collective intelligence in online global trolling: The case of trolling Trump's inauguration speech. *Information, Communication & Society*, 25(7), 1029-1044.
- Fichman, P., & Rathi, M. (2022). The impact of culture on online toxic disinhibition: Trolling in India and the USA. *Proceedings of the 55th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 5, 2890-2897.
- Fichman, P., & Vaughn, M. (2021). The relationships between misinformation and outrage trolling tactics on two Yahoo! Answers categories. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 72(12), 1498-1510.
- Flores-Saviaga, C. I., Keegan, B. C., & Savage, S. (2018). Mobilizing the trump train: Understanding collective action in a political trolling community. *Twelfth International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media, June 2018, California, USA*, pp. 82-91
- Grossmann, M., & Hopkins, D. A. (2016). *Asymmetric politics: Ideological Republicans and group interest Democrats*. Oxford University Press.
- Howard, P. N., Ganesh, B., Liotsiou, D., Kelly, J., & François, C. (2019). *The IRA, social media and political polarization in the United States, 2012-2018*. Project on computational propaganda. <https://comprop.oii.ox.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/sites/93/2018/12/The-IRA-Social-Media-and-Political-Polarization.pdf>
- https://pure.rug.nl/ws/portalfiles/portal/94315495/The_IRA_Social_Media_and_Political_Polarization.pdf Kim, D., Graham, T., Wan, Z., & Rizoiu, M. A. (2019). Analysing user identity via time-sensitive semantic edit distance (t-SED): A case study of Russian trolls on Twitter. *Journal of Computational Social Science*, 2(2), 331-351.
- Kennedy, I., Wack, M., Beers, A., Schafer, J. S., Garcia-Camargo, I., Spiro, E. S., & Starbird, K. (2022). Repeat spreaders and election delegitimization: A comprehensive dataset of misinformation tweets from the 2020 US election. *Journal of Quantitative Description: Digital Media*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.51685/jqd.2022.013>
- Lieback, H. (2019). Truth-telling and trolls: trolling, political rhetoric in the twenty-first century, and the objectivity norm. *Aspeers*, (12), 9-36.
- Linville, D. L., & Warren, P. L. (2020). Engaging with others: How the IRA coordinated information operation made friends. *Harvard Kennedy School Misinformation Review*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.37016/mr-2020-011>
- Murdani, A., Haqqi, H., & Alchatib, S. (2022). The role of social media and its implication for democracy in 2020 US elections. *Ilomata International Journal of Social Science*, 3(3), 325-336.
- Ortiz, S. M. (2020). Trolling as a collective form of harassment: An inductive study of how online users understand trolling. *Social Media+ Society*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2056305120928512>

- Polyakova, A. (2020). The kremlin's plot against democracy: How Russia updated its 2016 playbook for 2020. *Foreign Affairs*, 99(5), 140-149.
- Norri–Sederholm, T., Norvanto, E., Talvitie–Lamberg, K., & Huhtinen, A. M. (2020). Misinformation and disinformation in social media as the pulse of Finnish national security. In Moehlecke de Baseggio, E., Schneider, O., Szyrcsev Tresh, T. (Eds), *Social Media and the Armed Forces. Advanced Sciences and Technologies for Security Applications* (pp. 207-225). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-47511-6_12
- Rao, A., Morstatter, F. & Lerman, K. (2022). Partisan asymmetries in exposure to misinformation. *Sci Rep* 12, 15671. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-19837-7><https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-19837-7>
- Sanfilippo, M., Yang, S., & Fichman, P. (2017). Trolling here, there, and everywhere: Perceptions of trolling behaviors in context. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 68(10), 2313-2327.
- Sobieraj, S., & Berry, J. M. (2011). From incivility to outrage: Political discourse in blogs, talk radio, and cable news. *Political Communication*, 28(1), 19-41.
- Suler, J. (2004). The online disinhibition effect. *Cyberpsychology & behavior*, 7(3), 321-326.
- Vogels, E. A., Auxier, B., & Anderson, M. (2021). *Partisan differences in social media use show up for some platforms, but not Facebook*. Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2021/04/07/partisan-differences-in-social-media-use-show-up-for-some-platforms-but-not-facebook/>
<https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2021/04/07/partisan-differences-in-social-media-use-show-up-for-some-platforms-but-not-facebook/>
- Zelenkauskaite, A., & Niezgodna, B. (2017). “Stop Kremlin trolls:” Ideological trolling as calling out, rebuttal, and reactions on online news portal commenting. *First Monday*, [https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2021/04/07/partisan-differences-in-social-media-use-show-up-for-some-platforms-but-not-facebook/22\(5\)](https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2021/04/07/partisan-differences-in-social-media-use-show-up-for-some-platforms-but-not-facebook/22(5)).
<https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v22i5.7795><https://firstmonday.org/article/view/7795/6225><https://firstmonday.org/article/view/7795/6225>.